

Short communication

First record and a new synonymy of *Poecilus beesoni* (Coleoptera: Carabidae) from Iran

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چکیده

گونه *Poecilus beesoni* (Andrewes, 1927) که از کنار دریاچه ایذه در استان خوزستان جمع‌آوری شده است برای اولین بار از ایران گزارش می‌شود. برای شناسایی، نمونه‌های هولوتایپ این گونه و گونه *P. affinis* (Ali, 1967) مطالعه شدند. هم‌چنین گونه *Poecilus affinis* به عنوان سینونیم گونه *Poecilus beesoni* پیشنهاد می‌گردد.

In order to accurately identify the *Poecilus* species (Fig. 1) of Iran with the label “Iran Khuzestan/lake Izeh/ 1-IV-2007/ Muilwijk leg.”, the holotypes of *P. beesoni* (Andrewes, 1927) and *P. affinis* (Ali 1967) were studied. Both species have been originally described from Iraq based on single females. A male cotype of *P. beesoni* housed in the Natural History Museum, London, with the label “Basra/ 13-VI.1926/ Schmidt e./ H.E. Andrewes det.” was studied as well.

According to Ali (1966, 1967), *P. affinis* differs from *P. beesoni* in having three compressed basal antennomeres and weakly punctated pronotum. The second antennomere in *P. beesoni* is clearly less compressed than the third antennomere

As shown in Figure 2, only the third antennomere is clearly compressed in *P. affinis*. The pronotal punctation in the both holotypes of *P. affinis* and *P. beesoni* are also identical. Therefore, I consider *P. affinis* as a junior synonym of *P. beesoni*.

The species *Poecilus beesoni* has been collected from Izeh, a city in the Iranian province of Khuzestan and is newly recorded from Iran. This species was known from Iraq (Löbl & Smetana, 2003; Azadbakhsh & Nozari, 2015).

The colouration and pronotal punctation of *P. beesoni* are the result of intraspecific variation. The Iranian specimens are slightly more bluish than specimens from Iraq. Most Iranian specimens shine green along lateral side of the pronotum. Colour in *P. beesoni* (as in more *Poecilus* species) is rather variant; for example the cotype of *P. beesoni* is more bluish than *P. affinis*. Punctuation of basal fovea is always present. In some individuals the punctation of pronotum exceeds laterally to anterior side.

Acknowledgement

The author expresses his sincere thanks to Beulah Garner (Natural History Museum, London) for sending the holotypes for this study.

Fig. 1. FiHabitus of *Poecilus beesoni* from Izeh.

Fig. 2. *P. affinis* antennomeres I-III.

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Received: 13 February 2017

Accepted: 1 March 2017